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Research Article

**METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE
ESTIMATION OF NEBIVOLOL AND
HYDROCHLOROTHIAZIDE BY USING RP-HPLC METHOD**T.Kavitha Rani¹, M.Chaitnaya², P.Aravindra Reddy³¹Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy, N.F.C Nagar, Ghatkesar, Medchal, Telangana.**Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024****Abstract:**

High Performance Liquid Chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tools of the analysis. The estimation of Nebivolol, Hydrochlorothiazide was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer of pH 3.0 and the methanol as mobile phase was optimized with consists of Phosphate buffer and ACN (40: 60% v/v) Thermo Hypersil BDS, C18 and equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 282 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 0.8 ml/min. The linearity range of of Nebivolol and Hydrochlorothiazide were found to be from 6.25-37.5 µg/ml and 2.5-15 µg/ml of. Linear regression coefficient was found to be less than 0.999. The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 98-102% of Nebivolol and Hydrochlorothiazide. LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit. The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements. It inferred the method found to be simple, accurate, precise and linear. The method was found to be having suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

Key words: *Nebivolol, Hydrochlorothiazide, Validation, Linearity.***Corresponding author:****M.Chaitnaya,***Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION:

Nebivolol Hydrochloride, 1-(6-fl uorochroman-2-yl)-{[2-(6-fl uorochroman-2-yl)-2-hydroxy-ethyl]amino} ethanol is a white odourless powder used for the treatment of hypertension. Its mode of action is lowering blood pressure (BP) by reducing peripheral vascular resistance, and significantly increases stroke volume with preservation of cardiac output. The net hemodynamic effect of neбиволol is the result of a balance between the depressant effects of beta-blockade and an action that maintains the cardiac output.[1,2] Hydrochlorothiazide, 6-chloro-3,4-dihydro-7-sulfamoyl-2H-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine 1,1-dioxide is a white or almost white odorless powder used for the treatment of high blood pressure and management of edema. Hydrochlorothiazide promotes water loss from the body (diuretics). It inhibits Na(+)/Cl⁻ reabsorption from the distal convoluted tubules in the kidneys. It also causes loss of potassium and an increase in serum uric acid. It causes vasodilatation by activating calcium-activated potassium channels (large conductance) in vascular smooth muscles and inhibiting various carbonic anhydrases in vascular tissue.[3,4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

HPLC with WATERS, software: Empower, 2695 separation module, PDA detector. All chemicals were AR grade.

HPLC method development and validation:**Preparation of pH 6.5 phosphate buffer solution:**

Accurately weighed and transferred about 1.088gm of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and 0.021gm of dipotassium hydrogen phosphate in 400ml of HPLC grade water, sonicated to dissolve for five minutes then pH is was adjusted to 6.5±0.05 with dilute orthophosphoric acid solution and filtered.

Mobile phase:

Phosphate buffer and acetonitrile

Preparation of standard drug solution:

Accurately weighed and transferred 12.5mg of Hydrochlorothiazide (HCTZ) and 5mg of Nebivolol Hydrochloride (NBV) into a 50 ml volumetric flasks separately, about 30 ml of diluent was added, sonicated to dissolve for five minutes and then make up with diluent and mix. Transferred 1.0 ml of the above solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute to final volume with diluent.

Table 1: Optimized chromatographic conditions of the proposed RP-HPLC method

Parameters	Conditions
Column	Thermo Hypersil BDS, C18
Mobile Phase	Phosphate buffer and ACN (40: 60% v/v)
Flow rate	0.8 ml/min
Run time	10 min
Injection volume	20 µL
Detection wavelength	282 nm
Drug RT	2.482 and 4.001 min

Linearity of detector response:

By diluting aliquots (0.25-1.5 ml) of standard stock solution in 10 ml volumetric flasks with diluent to obtain concentrations in the range of 6.25-37.5µg/ml for HCTZ and 2.5-15µg/ml for NBV, respectively, a series of linearity solutions were prepared to demonstrate the linearity of an analytical method 20 µL of each conc level was injected into the chromatographic apparatus, and peak areas and chromatograms were analysed. Plotted a peak area versus concentration graph and used the calibration

graph to determine the correlation coefficient, slope, and intercept from calibration graph.

Intermediate/inter-day precision

The chromatographic apparatus was injected with a 20µL solution of standard preparations six times on two separate days. Chromatograms were recorded. percentage RSD was determined for retention time and peak areas of standard solutions of HCTZ & NBV as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of Intermediate (Inter-day) precision studies

S No.	Hydrochlorothiazide				Nebivolol Hydrochloride			
	Day-1		Day-2		Day-1		Day-2	
	Rt (min)	Peak Area	Rt (min)	Peak Area	Rt (min)	Peak Area	Rt (min)	Peak Area
1	2.489	2073445	2.490	2074446	4.002	1240506	4.012	1237257
2	2.485	2075243	2.488	2075545	4.005	1239545	4.011	1238751
3	2.481	2076115	2.485	2069578	4.001	1240425	4.008	1239945
4	2.492	2071626	2.486	2076125	4.011	1239140	4.001	1240445
5	2.488	2072245	2.482	2075145	4.008	1238756	4.007	1239125
6	2.482	2077452	2.491	2077315	4.008	1241045	4.011	1239865
Mean	2.486	2074354	2.487	2074692	4.006	1239903	4.008	1239231
SD	0.0043	2289.3	0.0033	2686.2594	0.0039	890.64	0.0041	1142.26
% RSD	0.171	0.110	0.135	0.129	0.097	0.072	0.102	0.092

The %RSD of retention times and peak areas for HCTZ and NBV obtained from six replicate the percentage relative standard deviation figures (less than 2%) show that the injections in the precision studies are consistent. Therefore, it can be said that the suggested RP-HPLC procedure is accurate.

Accuracy:

The test method's accuracy was illustrated by the percentage recovery across its range. Peak regions were measured and chromatograms were documented.

Table 3: Date of recovery studies

Sample	% Level of test Conc.	Peak area*	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	Mean % Recovery *± SD
HCTZ	80%	1651166	10.0	9.42	99.42 ±0.22
	100%	2074911	12.50	12.49	99.94±0.36
	120%	2502124	15.0	15.07	100.42± 0.42
NBV	80%	988473	4.0	3.98	99.58 ±0.35
	100%	1239202	5.0	4.99	99.87 ±0.57
	120%	1303235	6.0	6.04	100.66 ±0.23

The mean % recoveries from spiked samples were found to be in the range of 99.42-100.42% for HCTZ and 99.58-100.66% for NBV respectively, which were within the acceptance criteria limit.

and sample solutions were injected in triplicate to test the method's specificity for blank and placebo interference. Chromatograms from blank, placebo, standard, and sample solutions are compared to evaluate the specificity of the suggested RP-HPLC method.

Specificity:

As per the test procedure, blank, placebo, standard,

Table 4: Data of Specificity studies

Solution	Hydrochlorothiazide		Nebivolol		USP Resolution
	Rt (min)	Peak Area	Rt (min)	Peak Area	
Blank	-	-	-	-	-
Standard	2.487	2075835	4.005	1240215	6.82
Placebo	-	-	-	-	-
Sample	2.482	2073215	4.001	1239315	6.80

CONCLUSIONS:

The results of current study indicating that the retention time was found to be 2.482 min for Hydrochlorothiazide and 4.001 min for Nebivolol Hydrochloride. Quantitative linearity was obeyed in the concentration range of 6.25-37.50µg/ml for HCTZ and 2.5-15µg/ml for NBV respectively with correlation coefficient value of 0.9999. The percentage RSD for the peak areas of responses and retention times from precision studies were also found to be less than 2.0%, which advisable precise method. The high percentage recoveries indicate that the proposed method is highly accurate. Degradants produced during stress degradation studies were also well separated and did not obstruct the estimation of the drugs by the suggested stability indicating RP-HPLC method, as evidenced by the lack of interfering peaks in the chromatogram of blank and placebo interference studies. Based on the results of this investigation, the suggested stability indicating RP-HPLC method was determined to be sensitive, accurate, precise, dependable, and helpful for routine analysis of Nebivolol Hydrochloride and Hydrochlorothiazide in pharmaceutical dosage form and bulk.

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